

Abstract: This paper aims to give a general overview of the types of lexical cohesion in the English language. Together with grammatical cohesion, lexical cohesion forms one of the seven standards of textuality, namely cohesion. Therefore, a short explanation of the term itself as well as the difference between grammatical and lexical cohesion is given before focus is set on lexical cohesion and its different types. The types of lexical cohesion are the main topic of this paper. The given definitions and explanations aim to show what lexical cohesion is about, and the examples demonstrate how lexical cohesion works in a text. The types of lexical cohesion presented in this term paper refer to the classification of Schubert, who names the following ones: repetition, sense relations including synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy as well as meronymy, paraphrase, and collocation.

Key words: meaningful proximity, contact communication, distant communication, chain communication, intonation, connectors, connecting words, sentence fragments.

The text, like any whole, consists of its constituent elements, specific units. In linguistics, there is a lot of debate about what units form a text or what units are considered text units when dividing a text into parts. At first glance, it seems that defining text units is not such a difficult task. But in reality it is not so, that is why there are many and different views among text linguistics researchers. For example, a large whole that unites several sentences - a whole that is larger than a phrase - can be a unit of the text. It says that a sentence, which is a component of a larger whole than a phrase, cannot be the unity of the text at the same time. N.V. Nikolayeva suggested eight types of words. They are as follows: 1. International words that have the same meaning in two languages. 2. Compound words, as well as a combination of words whose components are familiar to students. 3. Words whose size does not contradict the semantic size of words in the native language. 4. Content-specific words for the target language. 5. Words that share the root with the native language, but differ in content, 6. Individual components, although known to students, are idiomatic, but close in meaning to the local meaning compounds and compound words that do not resemble words. 7. Words with a single lexical meaning wider than the meaning of the corresponding native language. 8. Lexical units, words whose size is equal to the size of their corresponding words in the native language. According to Shamov, a dictionary is a collection of words and their primary functions of associations that

make up a certain system¹². Vocabulary consists of vocabulary and lexical units. The number of lexical units studied at school is determined by the foreign language program for different types of schools. This size can be from 450 lexical units to 1200 lexical units.

These relationships are three types of conjunctions: syntactic means of communication connecting components in conjunctions without conjunctions, conjunctions and subordinate clauses: intonation, conjunctions, connecting words, clauses order, pronouns, repetition of certain words, common secondary clauses, tense relationship of participles, etc. It seems that syntactic connection is established between predicates in compound sentences. In the text, the syntactic connection should arise between whole sentences, superphrases, syntactic units, paragraphs, parts, sections, and chapters, and they should clarify each other in terms of content and structure, but also content.

Since cohesion does not only occur on a lexical level, but also on a grammatical- structural basis, the difference is stated at this point. While grammatical cohesion is based on the structural content of a text and how these structures are woven together, lexical cohesion is based on lexical knowledge and the way these lexical items are woven together . Consequently, grammatical cohesion looks at structure in a text, and lexical cohesion looks at the actual words. These grammatical structures are found on the surface of a text, while lexical cohesion already reaches underneath the surface, tackling the meaning of words. A prevalent type of lexical cohesion is repetition, also known as recurrence. If a word reoccurs in a different morphological form, e.g. altered by inflection, derivation, or compounding, we talk about partial repetition. Examples for partial repetition are:

- the use of nouns and compounds composed of these nouns: e. g. using pet, pets, pet dogs, dog, and dogs in the same text;
- the use of an adjective and its adverb in the same text: e. g. moral and morally;
- the use of the same word but in different word classes: the British (noun) and British people (adjective).Repetition contributes to clearness and continuity in text, which means it helps to avoid ambiguity. Nonetheless, very frequent repetition might reduce the level of informativity by producing redundancy.

Another type of lexical cohesion is the paraphrase. We speak of paraphrase if the meaning of a lexical item is expressed twice, not as in sense relations, but the second occurrence seeing to explain the first one using more words or even phrases. Therefore it is similar to synonymy, yet it is a longer form, using a more detailed

explanation rather than a single word similar in meaning. The aim of a paraphrase is usually to achieve greater clarity (Schubert 2008, 51f). Furthermore, Schubert mentions two directions of recurrence of meaning:

- Expansion: the second occurrence is more detailed or an explanation of the first one. E. g.: Some students disrupt the lessons. They constantly talk to their neighbours, play with their mobile phones, eat their lunch, and simply do not listen to the teacher. Here, the second sentence is explaining in detail the first one.

- Condensation: the first occurrence is the more detailed one, followed by the more general expression. E.g.: Clothes and toys were all over the floor, dirty pots, dishes and cutlery on the kitchen press and in the sink, the sofa was untidy with a pile of used tissues on top of it and underneath. The place was a complete mess. In this example, the second sentence summarises the first one.

CONCLUSION Thus, vocabulary is an extremely important aspect of language, and the ability to communicate in a foreign language depends on the level of formation of lexical skills and competencies. Vocabulary learning is a huge and time-consuming task, and the correct application of teaching principles guarantees a positive result. Didactic, linguistic, psychological and methodical are necessary for more effective teaching of vocabulary, vocabulary and It is necessary to teach the types of speech activities in relation to each other. Also, taking into account the selection criteria, the distribution of the lexicon and the classification of the lexicon, we selected lexical units in accordance with the topics of communicative lexical lessons of the 1-2 courses in the working program and science programs and developed a system of exercises based on these lexical units. Exercises play a central role in teaching a foreign language. The effectiveness of practical acquisition of a foreign language comes from the correct selection and use of exercises.

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